

Robot-based assessment of motor-cognitive dual-task abilities in unimpaired adults

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Abstract— The addition of a cognitive task to a balance task impacts postural control. While the effects of dual-tasks on the ability to maintain an upright posture in static conditions or during walking have been extensively investigated, a limited number of studies focused on dynamic balance scenarios. Even fewer studies have examined such scenarios while sitting. In this work, we explored how a motor-cognitive dual-task influenced balance in unimpaired individuals, in two age groups, under three different balance conditions while sitting. Subjects sat on a moving robotic seat that was either static, unstable as a plate on a pivot, or tilted following a preprogrammed motion trajectory. Subjects completed the single balance tasks, and the balance tasks plus both a digital version of the Stroop Test and a simple reaction time test, both administered using the robotic device's touchscreen. Since the Stroop test required active interaction with the screen, the reaction time test was included to determine whether the expected decline in balance performance during the cognitive task was solely due to cognitive load or also influenced by physical interaction with the screen. The study showed that, as expected, the cognitive task worsened balance performance, as shown by increased trunk movements. This effect was significant in all balance conditions except when the platform was moved following a preprogrammed trajectory. Meanwhile, the physical interaction with the screen did not significantly impact balance performance. Future studies will further investigate the dual-task paradigm by incorporating additional cognitive tasks and evaluating balance also while standing.

Keywords—dual-task, robotic seat, balance

I. INTRODUCTION

Several activities of daily living, such as walking while talking on the phone, are examples of motor-cognitive dual-tasks (MCDT). These involve simultaneously completing cognitive and motor tasks. Studies on unimpaired adults have shown that MCDT can worsen balance [1] and cognitive performance [2]. Indeed, the decline in performance occurs when the demand for cognitive resources exceeds individual capacity [3]. Further research has indicated that postural control requires higher cognitive effort in older than in young individuals, implying greater negative impact of MCDT on balance abilities [4]. While this aspect has been extensively investigated when standing in static conditions, less attention has been given to the effects of dual-task (DT) on dynamic balance. Even less attention has been given to such effects when sitting. Indeed, assessing balance in a seated position is fundamental, especially for individuals with lower limb impairments, as effective trunk control is crucial for their stability. Here, we explored for the first time postural responses to DTs while sitting, by using a robotic seat [5]. Subjects performed a Single balance Task (ST) and two DTs:

a Motor-Cognitive Dual-Task (MCDT): balance task plus a cognitive task based on the Stroop Color and Word Test (SCWT) and a Motor-Motor Dual-Task (MMDT) consisting of a balance task and a motor task based on a reaction time test, that measured subjects' reaction times. Both tasks involved the interaction with the touchscreen of the robotic device. For the common motor component of the aforementioned DTs, subjects were required to maintain their sitting balance under either static or dynamic conditions. These conditions were provided by the two-degree robotic seat of hunova, a medical robotic system developed by Movendo Technology (Genova, Italy). Our study had a twofold objective: firstly, examine how the DT influenced balance, anticipating a deterioration in postural performance. Secondly, since the MCDT required an interaction with the screen, we wanted to determine whether this deterioration was caused by the cognitive task alone or if it was ultimately impacted by the physical interaction with the screen.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Set up and protocol

This study utilized hunova, a medical robotic device featuring two electromechanical platforms, one under the feet and another under the seat, integrated with an inertial sensor to be placed on the sternum to track trunk motion. This device allows to perform balance tasks in both static and dynamic conditions. In this study, we focused on the platform under the seat. The DTs were performed in a static condition (S) and two dynamic balance conditions:

- D1: The platform was unstable, simulating a plate with a central pivot that tilted due to the user's weight shift, with an elastic force field, opposing the user's motion, attracting the platform to the horizontal position.
- D2: The platform imposed an external perturbation as it moved independently from the subjects' sway, following a pre-programmed circular trajectory (as done in [6]).

Each subject performed the selected balance task as Single-Task (ST), as MMDT and MCDT. The MMDT was based on a reaction time test, where subjects were instructed to touch an icon on the screen as soon as it changed color. The MCDT was based on the digital version of the SCWT. The SCWT includes three parts: 1) Word Reading (participants read color words in black ink), 2) Color Naming (participants name colors of neutral symbols), and 3) Interference (participants name ink colors of incongruent words, e.g., "red" printed in blue ink). The digital version replicated the classic SCWT but

Figure 1: Trunk movements across the two age groups (<35 yo and >60 yo) for each task (ST, MMDT, and MCDT part 1,2 and 3) in all three balance conditions (S, D1 and D2).

required participants to respond by touching one of four buttons corresponding to the displayed stimulus, while in the original format, verbal responses were given. The order of presentation of ST and DTs was randomized within each age group.

B. Subjects

The study was approved by the local ethical committee of the University of Genoa (protocol n. 2023/93 approved on 14/12/2023). Thirty-five people with no history of neurological disease were divided into two age groups: eighteen subjects under the age of 35 (26±3 years, 8 females (F) and 10 males (M)) and 17 subjects over the age of 60 (64±3 years, 13 F, 4 M).

C. Data and statistical analysis

To assess the subjects' balance performance, we extracted the standard deviation of the trunk accelerations of the inertial sensor on the torso. This measure strongly correlates with the postural sway computed from the displacement of the center of pressure and is a good indicator of balance performance [6]. To investigate our hypotheses, we performed a mixed-effects model with (i) age (under 35 over 60 yo), (ii) balance condition (S, D1 and D2), and (iii) task condition (5 levels: ST, MMDT, MCDT (part 1,2,3)) as dependent variables, the performance metrics as the independent variables, and subject as random factor.

III. RESULTS

As expected, balance performances of healthy subjects were influenced by balance condition and task condition (both $p < 0.001$); however, the influence of the task condition was different across each balance condition (interaction effect: $p = 0.048$). Results are shown in Figure 1. In S and D1, during the MCDT subjects showed bigger trunk movements than during the ST (all comparisons of ST with MCDT 1, 2 and 3 had p values < 0.001), with no differences across MCDT parts. The difficulty of the cognitive exercise did not influence balance performance while sitting. The addition of a motor task to the balance task, i.e., the MMDT, did not significantly affect balance performance, indicating that the pure interaction with the touchscreen while sitting did not cause any deterioration in balance. In contrast, for D2, although adding either a motor or cognitive task to the balance task resulted in larger trunk movements, these changes were not statistically significant. In these sitting tasks, we did not find any effect of age.

IV. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we evaluated DT abilities while sitting, as examining these types of tasks is particularly important for individuals with lower limb impairments, where trunk control is crucial. For our first objective we confirmed, as expected, that the addition of the cognitive task worsened balance performance, as indicated by increased trunk movements. However, this deterioration was significant in all balance conditions except for the externally imposed balance condition. This may be because in this case the trunk movements were already larger during the ST compared to the STs in the other balance conditions. For our second objective, we found that physical interaction with the device's touchscreen had no significant impact on balance performance, regardless of the balance condition. This ensured that the effect on balance performance observed in the MCDT was not influenced by the requirement for screen interaction during the cognitive task. Finally, no significant differences in balance performance were observed between younger and older adults, possibly because sitting tasks are generally less challenging than standing tasks. Understanding the effects on balance during DTs provides a useful reference point for comparison when studying these effects in populations with neurological diseases or following injuries. In light of this, future studies should explore the DT paradigm while standing, incorporating a variety of cognitive tasks, and eventually conducting trials with populations with sensorimotor or cognitive impairments. Such knowledge could support the development of target interventions, especially since many neurological disorders impair balance and coordination, which are further challenged during multitasking.

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DISCLAIMER

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